

Leader-Follower Formation Control of a Large-Scale Swarm of Satellite System using the State-Dependent Riccati Equation: Orbit-to-Orbit and in-Same-Orbit Regulation

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Abstract—The state-dependent Riccati equation (SDRE) is a nonlinear optimal controller with a flexible structure which is one of the main advantages of this method. Here in this work, this flexibility is used to present a novel design for handling a soft constraint for state variables (trajectories). The concept is applied to a large-scale swarm control system, with more than 1000 agents. The control of the swarm satellite system is devoted to two modes of orbit-to-orbit and in-same-orbit cases. Keeping the satellites in one orbit in regulation (point-to-point motion) requires additional constraints while they are moving in Cartesian coordinates. For a small number of agents trajectory design could be done for each satellite individually, though, for a swarm with many agents, that is not practical. The constraint has been incorporated into the cost function of optimal control and resulted in a modified SDRE control law. The proposed method successfully controlled a swarm case of 1024 agents in leader-follower mode for orbit-to-orbit and in-same-orbit simulations. The soft constraint presented a percentage of 0.05 in the error of the satellites with respect to travel distance, in in-same-orbit regulation. The presented approach is systematic and could be performed for larger swarm systems with different agents and dynamics.

I. INTRODUCTION

The state-dependent Riccati equation (SDRE) is a closed-loop optimal controller, similar to the linear quadratic regulator (LQR) though with a nonlinear structure [1]. This work focuses on a control problem of a swarm system including more than 1000 agents in the leader-follower scheme. The agents are satellites orbiting around Earth, therefore it is assumed that the gravity is compensated by the proper speed of the satellites in the orbit [2]–[4]. A large number of agents poses a challenge and makes it impractical to design trajectories for each agent individually. This motivated the embedding of a soft constraint in the cost function of the SDRE that results in a modified control law and a slightly different state-dependent differential Riccati equation

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Fig. 1. The schematic view of the i -th satellite on Earth orbit with r_{orbit} radius, presenting the thrusters and reaction-wheels schematic. It is assumed that the bi-directional thrust force and reaction torque exist in the 3D body frame of the satellite.

(SDDRE). In this systematic design, the position of the leader and the final configuration of agents are defined through an algorithm and all agents follow the leader while they try to keep the formation.

The introduced method only needs the final position of the leading agent in the global coordinate and the arrangement of the follower agents in the local coordinate. Leader follower topic was investigated in the SDRE research field, dedicating the application to control of two mobile robots [5], one leader and three follower satellites [6], one leader and three followers for a system of connected cranes, and 10 agents in leader-less consensus control [7], etc. Babazadeh and Selmic presented distance-based formation control of agents in a planar configuration and simulated up to 4 agents [8]. The swarm SDRE control could be applied to different case studies since the nonlinear dynamics change, and the controller is capable of working with different nonlinear systems. As long as the controllability of the system is satisfied, the coordinate and the model could vary which indicated the application of the SDRE for a wide range of dynamics.

The application of swarm control in this work is devoted to satellite control. The number of satellites is increasing very rapidly orbiting Earth. It is important to control them in terms of changing the orbits or positioning them (correcting or

defining new locations) in the same orbit. Avanzini et al. proposed attitude control using reaction wheels of the satellites in low orbits [9]. The reaction wheels were used to reorient the satellites or keep them steady during movements in space missions [10]–[13]. On-off actuation of thrusters of satellites is a practical input for translation of satellites/spacecraft in space [14]–[17]. Navabi et al. implemented adaptive fuzzy control for attitude control of satellites using on-off inputs [14]. This current work also considers the dynamics of the thrusters as on-off actuators, based on Ref. [6].

In the category of several satellite systems, there are two cases of the satellite constellation and formation flying; the latter includes trailing and swarm formations [18]. Bastante et al. studied the trailing orbits by satellites considering low thrust transfer optimization and gradient restoration algorithm [19]. Gambi et al. presented a swarm trailing formation for a series of 6 lightweight spacecraft; the application was devoted to the deflection of near-Earth asteroids by laser beams [20]. The other formation control methods were also investigated for satellites and spacecraft [21], [22]. The defined case in this work is in the swarm formation while preserving the same radial distance from the center of Earth; we refer to this case as in-same-orbit control throughout this paper. Moreover, this study is limited to orbits that are close to a circular shape. The population of the agents is significantly larger than the reported agents in the literature which shows the capacity of the proposed design for controlling swarms and systematic arrangements of the agents.

The main contributions of this paper are: 1) presenting a swarm SDRE control approach for handling a large-scale system of more than 1000 agents. 2) Presenting a modified control law based on a soft constraint to keep the same radial distance for all agents in the control task. 3) Presenting an algorithm to arrange an arbitrary number of agents in a sector of a sphere.

The second contribution is general in control theory and could be applied to different dynamical systems, unmanned aerial vehicles, robots, etc. to keep them in one specific trajectory while migrating to a new location; i.e. consider a mobile robot that is required to move from one point to another and at the same time should stay on a circular path or a direct line. For one or several limited robots this task could be done by trajectory design; however, for so many robots this action is not practical. Then with this proposed method, all the robots could move toward the target point and satisfy a general soft constraint for a desired trajectory.

The rest of the work is as follows. Section II presents the dynamics of the satellites and the coordinates. Section III expresses the SDRE control structure. Section IV shows the simulation results and Section V presents the concluding remarks.

II. SATELLITE SWARM DYNAMIC

The dynamic equations of a particular condition are studied, which is a system rotating around Earth in an orbit. The following assumptions are made to model the swarm system.

Assumption 1: The geometry of the orbits in modeling and control is assumed to be close to a circular shape.

Assumption 2: The generated forces by the solar wind, atmospheric drag, etc. are considered to be negligible with respect to the force of the thrusters and reaction wheels and the motion of the satellites.

Assumption 3: The satellite swarm system has enough initial speed to keep the system orbiting around Earth to compensate for the gravity in a steady condition. Then the propellant force of the thrusters is used to modify the course of motion in the same orbit or change the orbit.

The main fixed coordinate frame is set at the center of Earth, $\{X, Y, Z\}$ (m) and absolute values of the Euler angles are measured from fixed coordinate by $\xi_{2,i} = [\phi_i, \theta_i, \psi_i]^T$ (rad), see Fig. 1. The schematic view of the i -th satellite of the swarm system is depicted in Fig. 1, as a rectangular cuboid for the sake of simplicity. The system is fully actuated with three reaction wheels for orientation control and a propulsion system for generating bi-directional thrust in three main local axes. The body frame is placed at the center of mass (CoM) of the system. Note that Fig. 1 is a schematic and the thrusters of a satellite could be arranged in another shape with more actuators; the reaction wheels could be also designed inside the satellite. The i -th local coordinate axes are named $\xi_{1,i} = [x_{c,i}, y_{c,i}, z_{c,i}]^T$ (m) set at the CoM of the satellite. The linear velocity of the system in local coordinate is defined as $v_{1,i} = [u_i, v_i, w_i]^T$ (m/s) and the angular one as $v_{2,i} = [p_i, q_i, r_i]^T$ (rad/s).

The generated torque components by the reaction wheels are $\tau_{B,i} = \{\tau_{\phi,i}, \tau_{\theta,i}, \tau_{\psi,i}\}$ (N.m) and the generated force components in local axes are $F_{B,i} = \{F_{x,i}, F_{y,i}, F_{z,i}\}$ (N). Based on Assumption 1, the swarm system is orbiting Earth in a shape, relatively close to a circle, $r_{\text{orbit}} \approx \text{cte}$. It might deviate a little though in the control design, the objective is to have control over the motion in in-same-orbit regulation.

The kinematics relations between the global and local coordinates are as follows:

$$\dot{\xi}_{1,i} = \mathbf{R}_i(\xi_{2,i})v_{1,i}, \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{\xi}_{2,i} = \mathbf{T}_i(\xi_{2,i})v_{2,i}, \quad (2)$$

where

$$\mathbf{R}_i(\xi_{2,i}) = \begin{bmatrix} c_{\psi,i}c_{\theta,i} & -c_{\phi,i}s_{\psi,i} + s_{\phi,i}s_{\theta,i}c_{\psi,i} & s_{\phi,i}s_{\psi,i} + c_{\phi,i}s_{\theta,i}c_{\psi,i} \\ s_{\psi,i}c_{\theta,i} & c_{\phi,i}c_{\psi,i} + s_{\phi,i}s_{\theta,i}s_{\psi,i} & -s_{\phi,i}c_{\psi,i} + c_{\phi,i}s_{\theta,i}s_{\psi,i} \\ -s_{\theta,i} & c_{\theta,i}s_{\phi,i} & c_{\theta,i}c_{\phi,i} \end{bmatrix},$$

$$\mathbf{T}_i(\xi_{2,i}) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & s_{\phi,i}t_{\theta,i} & c_{\phi,i}t_{\theta,i} \\ 0 & c_{\phi,i} & -s_{\phi,i} \\ 0 & s_{\phi,i}/c_{\theta,i} & c_{\phi,i}/c_{\theta,i} \end{bmatrix}.$$

The kinetic energy of the i -th system is defined in the global coordinate:

$$K_{E,i} = \frac{1}{2} \left(m_{b,i}(\dot{\xi}_{1,i}^T \dot{\xi}_{1,i}) + \dot{\xi}_{2,i}^T \mathbf{I}_{b,i} \dot{\xi}_{2,i} \right),$$

where $\mathbf{I}_{b,i}(\xi_{2,i}) = \mathbf{T}_i^{-T}(\xi_{2,i})\mathbf{I}_{c,i}\mathbf{T}_i^{-1}(\xi_{2,i})$ is the inertia matrix in the global frame in which $\mathbf{I}_{c,i} = \text{diag}(I_{xx,i}, I_{yy,i}, I_{zz,i})$ (kgm²)

is the inertia matrix of the satellite in local principal axes. Considering the generalized coordinate vector of the system as $\mathbf{q}_i = \{x_{c,i}, y_{c,i}, z_{c,i}, \phi_i, \theta_i, \psi_i\}$, and using the Lagrange method, the equations of motions are found as:

$$m_{b,i} \ddot{\xi}_{1,i} = \mathbf{R}_i(\xi_{2,i}) \mathbf{F}_{B,i}, \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{J}_i(\xi_{2,i}) \ddot{\xi}_{2,i} = \tau_{B,i} - \mathbf{c}_i(\xi_{2,i}, \dot{\xi}_{2,i}), \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{J}_i(\xi_{2,i}) : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ is the inertia matrix of the rotational dynamics and $\mathbf{c}_i(\xi_{2,i}, \dot{\xi}_{2,i}) : \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$ includes the Coriolis and centrifugal terms.

Selecting the state vector of the i -th satellite as

$$\mathbf{x}_i = [\xi_{1,i}^\top, \xi_{2,i}^\top, \mathbf{v}_{1,i}^\top, \mathbf{v}_{2,i}^\top]^\top, \quad (5)$$

and computation of first derivative of \mathbf{x}_i , result in the state-space representation of the system:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}_i = [\dot{\xi}_{1,i}^\top, \dot{\xi}_{2,i}^\top, \dot{\mathbf{v}}_{1,i}^\top, \dot{\mathbf{v}}_{2,i}^\top]^\top. \quad (6)$$

Computing the time derivative of (1) and (2), and extracting $\dot{\mathbf{v}}_{1,i}$ and $\dot{\mathbf{v}}_{2,i}$ provide:

$$\dot{\mathbf{v}}_{1,i} = \mathbf{R}_i^{-1}(\xi_{2,i}) (\dot{\xi}_{1,i} - \dot{\mathbf{R}}_i(\xi_{2,i}) \mathbf{v}_{1,i}), \quad (7)$$

$$\dot{\mathbf{v}}_{2,i} = \mathbf{T}_i^{-1}(\xi_{2,i}) (\dot{\xi}_{2,i} - \dot{\mathbf{T}}_i(\xi_{2,i}) \mathbf{v}_{2,i}). \quad (8)$$

Substituting (3),(4),(7), and (8) into (6) represents it in the form of:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}_i = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_i(\xi_{2,i}) \mathbf{v}_{1,i} \\ \mathbf{T}_i(\xi_{2,i}) \mathbf{v}_{2,i} \\ \mathbf{R}_i^{-1}(\xi_{2,i}) \left(\frac{1}{m_{b,i}} \mathbf{R}_i(\xi_{2,i}) \mathbf{F}_{B,i} - \dot{\mathbf{R}}_i(\xi_{2,i}) \mathbf{v}_{1,i} \right) \\ \mathbf{T}_i^{-1}(\xi_{2,i}) \left(\mathbf{J}_i^{-1}(\xi_{2,i}) \{ \tau_{B,i} - \mathbf{c}_i(\xi_{2,i}, \dot{\xi}_{2,i}) \} - \dot{\mathbf{T}}_i(\xi_{2,i}) \mathbf{v}_{2,i} \right) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (9)$$

Actuators saturation and on-off thrusters: The thrust actuators of the satellites are on-off type [6]:

$$\mathbf{F}_{B,i} = \begin{cases} \mathbf{F}_{B,\max} \text{sign}(\mathbf{F}_{B,i}) & |\mathbf{F}_{B,i}| > \mathbf{F}_{B,\text{threshold}}, \\ \mathbf{0} & |\mathbf{F}_{B,i}| < \mathbf{F}_{B,\text{threshold}}, \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{F}_{B,\max}(N)$ is the maximum power of thrust which defines the ‘‘on’’ state of the actuator, and $\mathbf{F}_{B,\text{threshold}}$ defines the dead-band of the input, to put the actuator in ‘‘off’’ state. The threshold affects the number of switching and small values for $\mathbf{F}_{B,\text{threshold}}$ increases the precision of the control at the cost of more on-off jumps. The limits of the torque of the reaction wheels are also presented [23]:

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{B,\max,i} &= \tau_{B,\text{stall}} - \frac{\tau_{B,\text{stall}}}{\omega_{B,\text{nl}}} \mathbf{v}_{2,i}, \\ \tau_{B,\min,i} &= -\tau_{B,\text{stall}} - \frac{\tau_{B,\text{stall}}}{\omega_{B,\text{nl}}} \mathbf{v}_{2,i}, \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where $\tau_{B,\text{stall}}(\text{Nm})$ is the stall torque of the reaction wheels and $\omega_{B,\text{nl}}(\text{rad/s})$ is the no-load speed of that.

Arrangement of the swarm satellite system: The arrangement of a large-scale swarm of satellites in orbit needs an automatic algorithm that receives the number of agents and organizes them in a sector of a sphere (or in other shapes), presented in Fig. 2. For a small number of agents,

Fig. 2. A sector of a sphere for an arrangement of the swarm system on the orbit of Earth.

i.e. less than 10, it might be easy to define the positions of the satellites; however, for more than 1000 satellites, a systematic algorithm must be ready to arrange the swarm. The following algorithm defines the arrangements. The first step is to construct:

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for  $i = 1, \dots, N_n + 1$ ,
  for  $j = 1, \dots, N_n + 1$ ,
     $\alpha_{j+(i-1)N_{\text{agents}}} = A_j$ ,
  end,
end,

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where i, j are local counters, N_{agents} is the total number of the agents (it must be a square number, equal or greater than 4), $N_n = \sqrt{N_{\text{agents}}} - 1$, and $A = [\alpha_1 : \frac{\alpha_2 - \alpha_1}{N_n} : \alpha_2]$ in which $\alpha_1, \alpha_2(\text{rad})$ are the bounds of the α angle, presented in Fig. 2. The next ‘‘for’’ loop finalizes the arrangement of the agents:

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for  $i = 1, \dots, N_n + 1$ ,
  for  $j = 1 + (i-1)(N_n + 1), \dots, (N_n + 1)i$ ,
     $x_{c,f,j} = r_{\text{orbit}} \sin(\beta_i) \cos(\alpha_j)$ ,
     $y_{c,f,j} = r_{\text{orbit}} \sin(\beta_i) \sin(\alpha_j)$ ,
     $z_{c,f,j} = r_{\text{orbit}} \cos(\beta_i)$ ,
  end,
end,

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where $r_{\text{orbit}}(\text{m})$ is the desired radius of the orbit, $[x_{c,f,j}, y_{c,f,j}, z_{c,f,j}]^\top(\text{m})$ is the position of the j -th satellite in Cartesian coordinate, and $\beta = [\beta_1 : \frac{\beta_2 - \beta_1}{N_n} : \beta_2]$. Following the algorithm, Eqs. (12) and (13), the arbitrary number of agents could be set according to the boundaries of a sector of the sphere, presented in Fig. 2.

III. CONTROLLER DESIGN

A. SDRE for a Swarm System: Orbit-to-Orbit Regulation

The i -th nonlinear control system in state-dependent coefficient (SDC) parameterization, could be introduced as:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}_i = \mathbf{A}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{x}_i + \mathbf{B}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{u}_i, \quad (14)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the state vector, $\mathbf{u}_i \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is the input vector, and $\mathbf{A}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ and $\mathbf{B}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ are

held. n is the number of states, for each satellite $n = 12$, presented in (5), and m is the number of inputs, in this case $m = 6$, $\mathbf{u}_i = [\mathbf{F}_{B,i}^\top, \boldsymbol{\tau}_{B,i}^\top]^\top \cdot [\mathbf{A}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)\mathbf{x}_i]$ and $[\mathbf{B}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)\mathbf{u}_i]$ present a smooth vector-valued functions, piece-wise-continuous that satisfy the local Lipschitz condition, with the equilibrium point $\mathbf{f}_i(\mathbf{0}) = \mathbf{0}$ where $\mathbf{f}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) = \mathbf{A}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)\mathbf{x}_i$.

Condition 1. The SDC pair $\{\mathbf{A}_i(\mathbf{x}_i), \mathbf{B}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)\}$ is a controllable parameterization of system dynamics (9) [24].

The cost function integral of the SDRE is set [1]:

$$J_i = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^\infty \{\mathbf{x}_i^\top \mathbf{Q}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)\mathbf{x}_i + \mathbf{u}_i^\top \mathbf{R}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)\mathbf{u}_i\} dt, \quad (15)$$

where $\mathbf{Q}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is the weighting matrix of states and $\mathbf{R}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$ is the one for the inputs, symmetric positive semi-definite and definite, respectively.

Condition 2. The pair of $\{\mathbf{A}_i(\mathbf{x}_i), \mathbf{Q}_i^{1/2}(\mathbf{x}_i)\}$ is an observable parameterization of the system dynamics (9); $\mathbf{Q}_i^{1/2}(\mathbf{x}_i)$ is the Cholesky decomposition of $\mathbf{Q}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)$ in (15) [1].

The SDC parameterization of system (9) is designed as:

$$\mathbf{A}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{R}_i(\boldsymbol{\xi}_{2,i}) & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{T}_i(\boldsymbol{\xi}_{2,i}) \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & -\mathbf{R}_i^{-1}(\boldsymbol{\xi}_{2,i})\dot{\mathbf{R}}_i(\boldsymbol{\xi}_{2,i}) & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & -\mathbf{T}_i^{-1}\mathbf{J}_i^{-1}\mathbf{C}_i\mathbf{T}_i - \mathbf{T}_i^{-1}\dot{\mathbf{T}}_i \end{bmatrix},$$

$$\mathbf{B}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \frac{1}{m_{b,i}}\mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{T}_i^{-1}(\boldsymbol{\xi}_{2,i})\mathbf{J}_i^{-1}(\boldsymbol{\xi}_{2,i}) \end{bmatrix},$$

in which $\mathbf{c}_i(\boldsymbol{\xi}_{2,i}, \dot{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_{2,i}) = \mathbf{C}_i(\boldsymbol{\xi}_{2,i}, \dot{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_{2,i})\dot{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_{2,i}$ holds. Controllability of the SDC matrices is satisfied for $\boldsymbol{\xi}_{2,i}, \dot{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_{2,i}$, except for any combination of $\boldsymbol{\xi}_{2,i}$ which makes any diagonal components of $\mathbf{R}_i(\boldsymbol{\xi}_{2,i})$ and $\mathbf{T}_i(\boldsymbol{\xi}_{2,i})$ zero, or $\theta = (2k-1)\pi/2$ for $k \in \mathbb{Z}$ which makes $\mathbf{T}_i(\boldsymbol{\xi}_{2,i})$ matrix singular.

The control law of the i -th agent is [1]:

$$\mathbf{u}_i = -\mathbf{R}_i^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_i)\mathbf{B}_i^\top(\mathbf{x}_i)\mathbf{K}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)\mathbf{x}_i, \quad (16)$$

where $\mathbf{K}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is the symmetric positive-definite solution to the state-dependent Riccati equation:

$$\mathbf{A}_i^\top(\mathbf{x}_i)\mathbf{K}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) + \mathbf{K}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)\mathbf{A}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) - \mathbf{K}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)\mathbf{B}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)\mathbf{R}_i^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_i)\mathbf{B}_i^\top(\mathbf{x}_i)\mathbf{K}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) + \mathbf{Q}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) = \mathbf{0}, \quad (17)$$

which is updated by SDC matrices in (14) and weighting matrices in (15) at each time step of control loop.

Without loss of generality, to track the pattern of the satellites in algorithms (12) and (13), the control law (16) is modified as

$$\mathbf{u}_i = -\mathbf{R}_i^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_i)\mathbf{B}_i^\top(\mathbf{x}_i)\mathbf{K}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_{\text{des},i}), \quad (18)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_{\text{des},i} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the desired condition of the agents.

The first agent of the swarm is the leader of the group

$$\mathbf{x}_{\text{des},1} = [x_{c,f,1}, y_{c,f,1}, z_{c,f,1}, \phi_{\text{des},1}, \theta_{\text{des},1}, \psi_{\text{des},1}, \mathbf{0}_{1 \times 6}]^\top,$$

with a time-invariant (constant) desired condition. $x_{c,f,1}, y_{c,f,1}, z_{c,f,1}$ are found by (13) and $\phi_{\text{des},1}, \theta_{\text{des},1}, \psi_{\text{des},1}$

could be set arbitrary or zero. The time-varying desired condition of the followers are:

$$\mathbf{x}_{\text{des},i}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} x_{1,1}(t) + x_{c,f,i} - x_{c,f,1} \\ x_{1,2}(t) + y_{c,f,i} - y_{c,f,1} \\ x_{1,3}(t) + z_{c,f,i} - z_{c,f,1} \\ \phi_{\text{des},i} \\ \theta_{\text{des},i} \\ \psi_{\text{des},i} \\ \mathbf{0}_{6 \times 1} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \text{for } i = 2, \dots, N_{\text{agents}},$$

where $x_{1,1}(t), x_{1,2}(t), x_{1,3}(t)$ are the first to third actual states of the leader agent.

So, this section summarizes that from an initial point on one orbit, the swarm of satellites could be regulated to another surface in another orbit. The arrangement of the swarm from the initial condition could be also set as a sector of a sphere, though other shapes and patterns could be applied to the controller.

B. In-Same-Orbit SDRE Control

This section proposes the novelty of this work, controlling a swarm system (point-to-point motion) in the same orbit, or better to say, a repositioning of the swarm in the same radial distance from the center of Earth. The agents will be controlled in Cartesian coordinates and at the same time, the orbit of the motion will be kept close to a constant value:

$$r_{\text{orbit}}(t) = \sqrt{x_{c,i}^2(t) + y_{c,i}^2(t) + z_{c,i}^2(t)} \approx \text{cte.},$$

as a soft constraint to the optimal control problem. The nonlinear system representing an agent is similar to (14) with its condition; however, the cost function of optimal control is changed to incorporate the soft constraint and finite-time scheme:

$$J_{c,i} = \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{x}_i^\top(t_f)\mathbf{F}_i\mathbf{x}_i(t_f) + \frac{1}{2}\int_0^{t_f} \{\mathbf{x}_i^\top \mathbf{Q}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)\mathbf{x}_i + [\mathbf{u}_i + \mathbf{V}_i\mathbf{w}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)]^\top \mathbf{R}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)[\mathbf{u}_i + \mathbf{V}_i\mathbf{w}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)]\} dt, \quad (19)$$

where $\mathbf{F}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is the weighting matrix of states at the final time (symmetric positive semi-definite), t_f is the final time of the control task.

Remark 1: It should be noted that due to introducing the soft constraint in optimal cost function (19), the derivation of the Riccati equation generates a slightly different shape with an extra term. Therefore, the backward integration (BI) method is a solution to solve governing semi-Riccati equation and BI works with differential Riccati equation (not with the algebraic SDRE (17)). This is the reason for moving from infinite-horizon optimal control (15) in Section III-A to finite-horizon control design (19).

$\mathbf{V}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 3}$ is a positive control gain matrix to weight the soft constraint, and the constraint is:

$$\mathbf{w}_i(\mathbf{x}_i(t)) = \begin{bmatrix} r_{\text{orbit}}(t) - r_{\text{orbit,des}} \\ \dot{r}_{\text{orbit}}(t) - \dot{r}_{\text{orbit,des}} \\ \ddot{r}_{\text{orbit}}(t) - \ddot{r}_{\text{orbit,des}} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (20)$$

in which $r_{\text{orbit,des}}(m)$ is the desired orbit radius. Equation (20) includes the error of orbit radius along with its velocity

and acceleration. The Hamiltonian is built in the form of

$$\mathcal{H}_i(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{u}_i, \boldsymbol{\lambda}_i) = \frac{1}{2} \{ \mathbf{x}_i^\top \mathbf{Q}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{x}_i + [\mathbf{u}_i + \mathbf{V}_i \mathbf{w}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)]^\top \mathbf{R}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) [\mathbf{u}_i + \mathbf{V}_i \mathbf{w}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)] \} + \boldsymbol{\lambda}_i^\top [\mathbf{A}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{x}_i + \mathbf{B}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{u}_i],$$

using system (14) and cost function (19) where $\boldsymbol{\lambda}_i$ is the co-state vector of the i -th agent. The stationary condition [25]:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{H}_i(\cdot)}{\partial \mathbf{u}_i} = \mathbf{0},$$

generates

$$\mathbf{R}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) [\mathbf{u}_i + \mathbf{V}_i \mathbf{w}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)] + \mathbf{B}_i^\top(\mathbf{x}_i) \boldsymbol{\lambda}_i = \mathbf{0},$$

which results in the modified control law, considering $\boldsymbol{\lambda}_i = \mathbf{K}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{x}_i$:

$$\mathbf{u}_i = -\mathbf{R}_i^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{B}_i^\top(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{K}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{V}_i \mathbf{w}_i(\mathbf{x}_i). \quad (21)$$

The control law (21) includes the soft constraint of the optimal control in addition to the main regulation part of the conventional input law of the SDRE. Then the necessary condition for optimality

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{H}_i(\cdot)}{\partial \mathbf{x}_i} = -\dot{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}_i,$$

provides:

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbf{Q}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{x}_i + \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{x}_i^\top \frac{\partial \mathbf{Q}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)}{\partial \mathbf{x}_i} \mathbf{x}_i + \frac{1}{2} [\mathbf{u}_i + \mathbf{V}_i \mathbf{w}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)]^\top \\ & \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)}{\partial \mathbf{x}_i} [\mathbf{u}_i + \mathbf{V}_i \mathbf{w}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)] + [\mathbf{u}_i + \mathbf{V}_i \mathbf{w}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)]^\top \mathbf{R}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \\ & \frac{\partial [\mathbf{V}_i \mathbf{w}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)]}{\partial \mathbf{x}_i} + \mathbf{x}_i^\top \mathbf{A}_i^\top(\mathbf{x}_i) \boldsymbol{\lambda}_i + \mathbf{x}_i^\top \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{A}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)}{\partial \mathbf{x}_i} \right)^\top \boldsymbol{\lambda}_i + \\ & \mathbf{u}_i^\top \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)}{\partial \mathbf{x}_i} \right)^\top \boldsymbol{\lambda}_i = \dot{\mathbf{K}}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{x}_i + \mathbf{K}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \dot{\mathbf{x}}_i. \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

Substituting (14) and co-state vector into (22) generates:

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbf{Q}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{x}_i + \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{x}_i^\top \frac{\partial \mathbf{Q}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)}{\partial \mathbf{x}_i} \mathbf{x}_i + \frac{1}{2} [\mathbf{u}_i + \mathbf{V}_i \mathbf{w}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)]^\top \\ & \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)}{\partial \mathbf{x}_i} [\mathbf{u}_i + \mathbf{V}_i \mathbf{w}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)] + [\mathbf{u}_i + \mathbf{V}_i \mathbf{w}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)]^\top \mathbf{R}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \\ & \frac{\partial [\mathbf{V}_i \mathbf{w}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)]}{\partial \mathbf{x}_i} + \mathbf{x}_i^\top \mathbf{A}_i^\top(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{K}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{x}_i + \\ & \mathbf{x}_i^\top \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{A}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)}{\partial \mathbf{x}_i} \right)^\top \mathbf{K}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{x}_i + \mathbf{u}_i^\top \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)}{\partial \mathbf{x}_i} \right)^\top \mathbf{K}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{x}_i = \\ & -\dot{\mathbf{K}}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{K}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{A}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{x}_i + \mathbf{K}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{B}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{R}_i^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_i) \\ & \mathbf{B}_i^\top(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{K}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{x}_i + \mathbf{K}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{B}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{V}_i \mathbf{w}_i(\mathbf{x}_i). \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Arranging the terms without derivatives of (23) in one equation, then factorization of \mathbf{x}_i from the right-hand side of that result in:

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbf{A}_i^\top(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{K}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) + \mathbf{K}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{A}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) - \\ & \mathbf{K}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{B}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{R}_i^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{B}_i^\top(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{K}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) + \mathbf{Q}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) - \\ & \mathbf{K}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{B}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{V}_i \mathbf{w}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{x}_i^\dagger = -\dot{\mathbf{K}}_i(\mathbf{x}_i). \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

Fig. 3. The error reduction of the 1024 satellites in orbit-to-orbit regulation.

Fig. 4. The trajectories of the 1024 satellites in orbit-to-orbit regulation. Clearer motion and visualization could be seen in the video file of the simulation as supplementary material for this paper.

where \mathbf{x}_i^\dagger is the generalized inverse of \mathbf{x}_i . Equation (24) does not possess the standard form of Riccati equation for the term $\mathbf{K}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{B}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{V}_i \mathbf{w}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{x}_i^\dagger$, therefore backward integration method will be used to solve this equation which is not sensitive to the shape of the equation and delivers a finite-time $\mathbf{K}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)$ for the control law (21).

Remark 2: In another approach, one could neglect the terms $\dot{\mathbf{K}}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)$ and $\mathbf{K}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{B}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{V}_i \mathbf{w}_i(\mathbf{x}_i) \mathbf{x}_i^\dagger$ from (24) and solve the Riccati equation (17) to find $\mathbf{K}_i(\mathbf{x}_i)$ and use it in (21). The second method would deliver a simpler solution, but less precise, for in-same-orbit simulation.

In Section IV-B, equation (24) is solved via the backward integration method to show the performance of the proposed finite-horizon optimal controller and capacity of the approach for solving a large-scale swarm system.

IV. SIMULATIONS

A. Orbit-to-Orbit

A system of 1024 satellites in a swarm of leader-follower scenario is considered for the simulation. The agents are moving in an initial orbit, $r_{\text{orbit}}(0) = 8871(\text{km})$ scattered randomly on a surface of a sector of a sphere with corresponding boundaries $\beta(0) = [0.75, 0.85](\text{rad})$ and $\alpha(0) = [0.25, 0.35](\text{rad})$. The objective of the control task is to regulate the leader to another orbit, closer to Earth while 1023 agents follow it keeping the final arrangement of the satellites, defined by Eq. (13). The simulation time is $t_f = 10000(\text{s})$, 2 hours 46 minutes and 40 seconds. The final orbit is $r_{\text{orbit}}(t_f) = 7371(\text{km})$ which defines a 1500(km) travel only in the radial direction (considering the motion in other directions, the travel distance increases). The boundaries of the final arrangement of the agents are set by $\beta(t_f) = [0.6, 1.1](\text{rad})$ and $\alpha(t_f) = [-0.2, 0.8](\text{rad})$, based on Fig. 2. The mass of each agent is considered 500(kg), size of each satellite is a rectangular cuboid $3 \times 4 \times 2(\text{m})$ with respect to x, y, z axes. The moment of inertia of agents are defined as $\mathbf{I}_{c,i} = \text{diag}(833.33, 541.66, 1041.7)(\text{kgm}^2)$, the maximum thrust of each actuator is $F_{B,\text{max,min}} = \pm 1000(\text{N})$, the threshold the thrusters is $F_{B,\text{threshold}} = 10(\text{N})$. The actuator characteristics for reaction wheels are also defined by $\tau_{B,\text{stall}} = 2(\text{Nm})$ and $\omega_{B,\text{nl}} = 5(\text{rad/s})$.

The weighting matrices of the states and inputs are selected as

$$\mathbf{Q}_i = \text{diag}(0.000001 \times \mathbf{1}_{1 \times 3}, \mathbf{1}_{1 \times 6}, 5 \times \mathbf{1}_{1 \times 3}),$$

$$\mathbf{R}_i = \mathbf{I}_{6 \times 6}.$$

The error reduction of the 1024 agents is presented in Fig. 3, completed. The configuration of the agents in orbit-to-orbit regulation has been presented in Fig. 4. The trajectories of the swarm are not clear in this picture due to a large number of agents, so a series of videos and graphical representations are shown as supplementary material for this simulation. The leader moves faster regulating towards the final condition, the follower agents then track the leader, while keeping the final pattern of distribution on the sector of the sphere. To show the complexity of the simulated system, the states and inputs of the third agent are illustrated in Figs. 5 and 6, respectively. Each agent has 12 states and 6 inputs. Three thrust forces of inputs are on-off types according to the dynamics of the satellites/spacecraft thrusters. To have a better view of the arrangement of the agents and the corresponding trajectories, 16 agents were simulated and illustrated in Fig. 7.

B. Same-Orbit

In this section, the objective is to keep the swarm system (1024 agents) in the same orbit (same radial distance from the center of Earth while repositioning the satellites), $r_{\text{orbit}}(t) \approx 7371(\text{km})$ in $t \in [0, t_f](\text{s})$, while the swarm is moving from one sector to another final destination. The initial positions of the satellites are limited in the boundaries of $\beta(0) = [1.6, 2.1](\text{rad})$ and $\alpha(0) = [0.4, 1.4](\text{rad})$, and the final arrangement is limited by $\beta(t_f) = [0.5, 1.2](\text{rad})$ and

Fig. 5. The states of the 3rd agent in orbit-to-orbit regulation as an example to show the complexity of the dynamics of each system. The satellites move fast though the definition of thrust limits could give a more realistic motion speed that could be set with the availability of a realistic model and platform for simulation.

Fig. 6. The inputs of 3rd agent in orbit-to-orbit regulation; on-off actuation of the thrusts presented in a-c.

$\alpha(t_f) = [-0.2, 0.8](\text{rad})$. The parameters of the controller, model, and weighting matrices are similar, only a new weighting matrix for final states is introduced:

$$\mathbf{F}_i = 0.1 \times \mathbf{Q}_i.$$

The new constraint matrix is:

$$\mathbf{V}_i = \begin{bmatrix} 1.5 & 50 & 5 \\ 1.8 & 40 & 5 \\ 0.4 & 30 & 5 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

The error of the agents for the in-same-orbit regulation also successfully converged towards zero, presented in Fig. 8. The trajectories of the swarm system are illustrated in Fig. 9. The soft constraint performance of the controller could be observed in Fig. 10. The largest value is approximately 4(km) at the beginning of the motion (the transient state of the control) which is acceptable based on the travel distance which is more than 8000(km). This indicates that the soft constraint kept the agents close in the same orbit with 0.05%

Fig. 7. The trajectories of 16 agents in the same simulation for having a clear view of the motion of the agents and the final arrangement of the system.

Fig. 8. The error reduction of the 1024 satellites in in-same-orbit regulation.

error with respect to travel distance. It should be noted that a simulation without the soft constraint would generate a migration while trajectories would pass through Earth, which is not correct, nor possible.

Remark 3: It is clear that if a slight modification for satellites is needed, i.e. a less than 1(km) motion, which imposes a small change in the position of the agents, the errors would be negligible.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This work presented a study on the control implementation of a large-scale swarm system in which the agents are satellites. The satellites should work in two modes of orbit-to-orbit and in-same-orbit regulation. The contribution of this work is on the design of the soft constraint for

Fig. 9. The trajectories of the 1024 satellites in in-same-orbit regulation. A better visualization is presented in a video file as supplementary material for the paper.

Fig. 10. The variation of the orbit error as a soft constraint for 1024 agents in in-same-orbit regulation. The travel distance is more than 8000(km) and the deviation of the agents from desired orbit is less than 0.05% in the transient state of the control task.

keeping the agents in the same orbit while they are being regulated to the final arrangement. The control works in a leader-follower scheme. The leader will go towards the final condition in global coordination; however, the agents try to keep the sector-of-sphere shape in control task locally. Both scenarios (orbit-to-orbit and in-same-orbit) were simulated successfully and the control structure of the novel SDRE with soft constraint was reported in control design, Section III-B. The error of the soft-constraint performance was gained less than 0.05% with respect to travel distance.

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